

A quality circle team to reduce falls in hospital wards

Dr Tak-Kwan Kong, Consultant Geriatrician in-charge, Department of Medicine & Geriatrics, Princess Margaret Hospital

Princess Margaret Hospital Task Group on Prevention of Fall

Project: A quality improvement team to reduce falls in wards

Background

Falls in hospitals have undesirable consequences, including injuries, immobility from fear of falls, increased length of stay in hospital, and patient complaints and litigations. The Quality Assurance Team of the Central Nursing Division of Princess Margaret Hospital (PMH) identified 381 patients falls from Jan 1993 to July 1994, an average of 20 falls per month, 62% of falls occurred in patients aged over 60. However, the format of incident reports on patient falls was not helpful in identifying preventable factors. Literature review showed there are multiple causative risk factors for falls, which can be grouped under Drugs, Age-related changes in gait/balance, Activities, Medical and Environmental causes. The D.A.M.E. Operation on Prevention of Fall was formed from a multi-disciplinary team under the PMH Task Group on Prevention of Fall to identify the causative factors for patient falls in PMH and suggest measures for prevention.

Methods

The multi-disciplinary team members of The D.A.M.E. Operation on Prevention of Fall consisted of doctors and nurses from various departments, a pharmacist, an occupational therapist, and a physiotherapist. For every reported fall incident during the study period, assessments were made on medical risk factors, the setting of the fall incidence, the drugs taken, environmental hazards, and gait and mobility problems. The team met monthly to identify the causative factors for patient falls in PMH and suggested measures for prevention.

The implementation consisted of 3 stages:

1. Recording and analysis of the causative risk factors of patient falls in PMH for a 3-month period (April to July 1995)
2. Formulation, dissemination, and implementation of guidelines for prevention of falls for a 4-month period (July to Nov 1995)
3. Re-analysis of the incidence and causes of falls for a 3-month period (Nov 1995 to Feb 1996)

Results

The high-risk drugs identified during the first phase of study before intervention were central nervous system depressants (28%), antihypertensives (22%), diuretics (9%), vasodilators (4%), and hypoglycaemics (4%). The age-related risk factors were impaired vision (22%) and unsteady gait (11%). The activities risk factors were toileting (37%) and transfer. The medical risk factors were hypovolaemia (20%), mobility limited by pain/ weakness/ chronic illness (17%), stroke (9%), impaired mental function (7%), post-partum (7%), foot problems (4%), neurosurgical patients (4%), sedation (2%), and parkinsonism (2%). The environmental risk factors were inappropriate bed height, bed pan on plastic chair, bedside rails, and movable furniture.

Identification of these high-risk factors on falls in wards and subsequent implementation of guidelines on fall prevention resulted in reduction of fall rate in wards by 13.7%

Fall risk factors	Before guidelines (n=46)	After guidelines (n=37)	p
Drugs	16(35%)	2(5%)	<0.001
Age-related	14(30%)	7(19%)	0.115
Activity	17(37%)	12(32%)	0.333
Medical	31(67%)	31(84%)	0.044
Environmental	29(63%)	8(22%)	<0.001

Conclusion

A proactive multidisciplinary team approach in identifying risk factors for falls in wards, and subsequent formulation, dissemination and implementation of falls prevention guidelines resulted in significant reduction in fall rate in wards by 13.7%. The most significant impact of the intervention was on risk factors related to drugs and environment.